

Artificial Experience (AE) in Decision-Making for Displaced Greater Tuberosity in Four-Part Proximal Humerus Fracture

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Introduction

“AI technology can significantly enhance decision-making processes in managing proximal humeral fractures, especially when considering surgical interventions.” ⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾

“AI can play a significant role in the decision-making process for managing malunion of the greater tuberosity, which is a common complication after proximal humeral fractures.” ⁽³⁾

“Predictive Modeling: AI can use data from previous cases to predict outcomes based on different treatment options. By analyzing factors such as age, activity level, and severity of the malunion, AI can help clinicians evaluate the likely success of surgical versus non-surgical interventions.” (*ChatGPT, August 17, 2024*)

AI requires data from past surgeries to enhance decision-making processes in orthopedic surgery. Collecting this data is a crucial preliminary step to unlock the full potential of AI in the field.

“Fracture Classification: AI can assist in accurately classifying the fracture type using advanced imaging analysis (such as CT or MRI scans). Automated systems can help radiologists identify the complexity of the fracture and guide treatment decisions.” (*ChatGPT, August 17, 2024*)

To use Fracture Classification as a guide for treatment decisions in Orthopedics, is an old option in decision-making, probably not the best one. Artificial Experience uses a different approach, it skips fracture classification and looks for independent isolated features of each case.

“Experience is direct observation of or participation in events as a basis of knowledge.” (*ChatGPT, August, 17, 2024*)

“Experience are memories (images) stored in your brain. The brain processes and organizes these experiences allowing you to recall them later and learn from them.” (*ChatGPT, August, 17, 2024*)

In the context of orthopedics, clinical experience consists of the firsthand involvement in diagnosing, treating, and managing orthopedic cases, where these cases serve as pivotal events that contribute to a clinician's body of knowledge.

When images are digitally recorded and stored, they can be referred to as a **recorded experience**. These recorded images can be high-definition and safeguarded against

manipulation, making them more reliable than human memories. However, they can be more challenging to access when needed. By incorporating the recorded experiences of multiple surgeons through unselected continuous series of cases and utilizing a search tool, we can define this integration as **Artificial Experience**.

“Artificial Intelligence is increasingly being utilized as a decision-making tool in orthopedic surgery, enhancing various aspects of patient care, surgical planning, and outcomes.” (ChatGPT, August, 17, 2024).

Artificial Experience represents a significant advancement in the field. One promising development is a comprehensive database created from preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative images of continuous, unselected cases from multiple orthopedic surgeons, akin to platforms like **icuc.net**.⁽⁸⁾ This database would be integrated with a powerful search tool, similar to **ICUC Tags***, serving as the foundation for what could evolve into a broader family of Artificial Experience applications in orthopedic.

Research Question:

Are limitations in abduction and external rotation, along with shoulder pain due to subacromial impingement, expected outcomes after a displaced, non-reduced greater tuberosity in a four-part proximal humerus fracture, or are they outcomes that may or may not occur?⁽³⁾⁽⁴⁾⁽⁵⁾⁽⁶⁾⁽⁷⁾

Can Artificial Experience (AE) Assist in Decision-Making for Displaced Greater Tuberosity in Four-Part Proximal Humerus Fractures?

Material and Methods

This study analyzes 134 cases of Proximal Humeral Fractures recorded in ICUC Tags* as of August 2024, comprising 72 operative cases and 62 nonoperative cases.

Among these, 26 cases were tagged as “Large Joint Step” with 14 occurring in the operative group and 12 in the nonoperative group.

* ICUC Tags is a search tool designed to enhance case retrieval by assigning a unique tag to each feature of every individual case.

Results

Operative Group: Of the 72 operative cases, 14 were identified with a “Large Joint Step” tag; however, 2 were discarded due to the following reasons:

- EA-486: Not an acute case, referred.
- AD-223: Fracture dislocation.

This leaves 12 cases for analysis. In these cases:

- 8 had a reduced joint step.
- 4 had a remaining joint step post-surgery, with 1 case undergoing reoperation the following day.

Outcomes in the Operative Group: Among the 12 cases analyzed:

- 4 cases did not have an ICUC score recorded.
- 8 cases had recorded ICUC scores:
 - 4 showed good or very good outcomes (3 reduced step, 1 non-reduced).
 - 2 had fair outcomes (1 reduced step, 1 non-reduced).
 - 2 had poor outcomes (both with reduced step).

Outcomes in the Nonoperative Group: Among the 12 non-operative cases with the “Large Joint Step” tag:

- All 12 had an ICUC score recorded:
 - 9 achieved good or very good outcomes.
 - 1 had a fair outcome.
 - 2 were classified as poor outcomes.

Discussion

Notably, good results were observed in:

- 10 cases with greater tuberosity that were not reduced (9 non-operative, 3 operative).

Poor results were found in:

- 2 non-operative cases that were not reduced, and
- 2 operative cases that had reduced steps (one of which resulted in avascular necrosis).

Interestingly, there were good results in cases with poorly reduced greater tuberosity, and poor outcomes were reported in one correctly reduced case.

Conclusion

Based on the analyzed data, it cannot be conclusively determined whether reduction of the greater tuberosity is mandatory for achieving a good outcome. Detailed case analysis, potentially facilitated by Artificial Experience, could aid surgeons in making more informed decisions.

References

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10. ICUC Tags

Figures

Fig. 1: Operative Treatment

A) Example of a perfectly reduced joint step with an excellent outcome. ICUC score⁽⁹⁾: FL=0, P=0. ICUC Score⁽⁹⁾ rates from 0 to 4, where 0 is the best possible outcome, and 4 the worst one.

B) Example of an unreduced joint step with an unknown outcome.

C) Example of an unreduced joint step with a good outcome. ICUC score⁽⁹⁾: FL=1, P=0.

Fig. 2: Non-Operative Treatment

Example of a good result despite an unreduced joint step. ICUC score⁽⁹⁾: FL=0, Pain=0.

Operative treatment, Greater Tuberosity (Examples)

A) Reduced Joint step	<p style="text-align: center;">11-VI-155 / 30y Female</p> <p>PRE 22w 30w</p> <p>ICUC Score Functional Limitation: 0 Pain: 0</p>	ICUC Score at 30w FL0 P0
B) Not-reduced Joint step	<p style="text-align: center;">11-VI-456 / 65y</p> <p>PRE 104w</p>	No ICUC Score
C) Not-reduced Joint step	<p style="text-align: center;">11-VI-847 / 55y Male</p> <p>PRE 79w</p>	ICUC Score at 219w FL1 P1

Figure 1

Figure 2